

Statistical Convergence Sequences in Neutrosophic Metric Spaces

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Abstract. In this study, motivated by the notion of statistical convergence in intuitionistic fuzzy metric space, we present the ideas of statistical convergence and Cauchy sequences with regard to the neutrosophic metric spaces. This study also discusses the statistical completeness on neutrosophic metric space with an example and results.

Keywords: Neutrosophic metric; Statistically convergent sequence; Statistically Cauchy sequence

1. Introduction

In 2004, utilising the intuitionistic fuzzy set [1], Fuzzy Metric Spaces (\mathfrak{FMS}) has been widened to Intuitionistic Fuzzy Metric Space (\mathfrak{IFMS}) by Park [13]. Park used continuous triangular norms as well as continuous triangular conorms to describe this idea. For \mathfrak{FMS} , Changqing et al. [4] developed Statistical Convergence (\mathfrak{SC}) sequences in 2020. On \mathfrak{IFMS} , similar ideas were used by several authors and their work, who achieved considerable outcomes. Fast [5] established the concept of \mathfrak{SC} in 1951, garnering interest from researchers across both purely mathematical and practical disciplines. \mathfrak{FMS} and \mathfrak{IFS} were used for investigating several new breakthroughs, including fixed point theories and convergence by Granados et al [7]. In \mathfrak{NMS} , similar outcomes can be derived by Jeyaraman et al [9]. In [10], Kramosil and Michalek presented the idea of \mathfrak{FMS} . Fuzzy sets were first presented by Zadeh [21], and numerous writers have since addressed their notions under numerous contexts, including \mathfrak{FMS} .

The concept of generalization of convergence, denoted by \mathfrak{GC} , is defined as follows: Let $\mathfrak{M} \subseteq \mathfrak{IN}$, where \mathfrak{IN} represents the set of all positive integers. For every $\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{IN}$, $\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{n})$ is defined as $\{\lambda \leq \mathfrak{n} : \lambda \in \mathfrak{M}\}$. The natural (or asymptotic) density of \mathfrak{M} , denoted by $\Delta(\mathfrak{M})$, is defined by $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{n})|}{\mathfrak{n}}$ if the limit exists, where $|\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{n})|$ represents the cardinality of the set $\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{n})$. The value of $\Delta(\mathfrak{M})$ lies in the interval $[0, 1]$ and satisfies $\Delta(\mathfrak{IN} \setminus \mathfrak{M}) = 1 - \Delta(\mathfrak{M})$ if $\Delta(\mathfrak{M})$ exists.

For instance, $\Delta(\mathfrak{I}\varrho) = 1$, $\Delta(\mathfrak{P}) = \frac{1}{2}$ where \mathfrak{P} denotes the set of even positive integers, and $\Delta(\mathfrak{B}) = 0$ where \mathfrak{B} is a finite subset of \mathfrak{IN} . A set \mathfrak{M} is considered statistically dense if $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}) = 1$. A sequence $(\zeta_n) \subset \mathfrak{IR}$ is said to be \mathfrak{GC} to $\zeta_0 \in \mathfrak{IR}$ if for every $\epsilon > 0$, the condition $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{IN} : |\zeta_n - \zeta_0| < \epsilon\}) = 1$ is satisfied, where \mathfrak{IR} denotes the set of all real numbers. Numerous significant results on \mathfrak{GC} have been presented by various authors ([?]- [19]).

in this work, convergent and \mathfrak{GC} relations in $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$ are then investigated. On $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$, we also investigate $\mathfrak{GC}\mathfrak{a}$ sequences and statistical completeness.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [7] Let κ , ϱ , and φ be fuzzy sets on $\Omega^2 \times (0, \infty)$, where \odot is a continuous triangular norm and \oplus is a continuous triangular conorm. We say that $(\kappa, \varrho, \varphi)$ forms a Neutrosophic Metric (\mathfrak{NM}) on Ω if κ and ϱ satisfy the following conditions:

- (1) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) + \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) + \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) \leq 3$;
- (2) $0 < \kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) < 1$, $0 < \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) < 1$ and $0 < \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) < 1$;
- (3) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) > 0$;
- (4) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = 1 \iff \zeta = \xi$;
- (5) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \kappa(\xi, \zeta, \varpi)$;
- (6) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) \odot \kappa(\xi, \tilde{v}, \mathbf{u}) \leq \kappa(\zeta, \tilde{v}, \varpi + \mathbf{u})$;
- (7) $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous;
- (8) $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) > 0$;
- (9) $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = 0 \iff \zeta = \xi$;
- (10) $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \varrho(\xi, \zeta, \varpi)$;
- (11) $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) \oplus \varrho(\xi, \tilde{v}, \mathbf{u}) \geq \varrho(\zeta, \tilde{v}, \varpi + \mathbf{u})$;
- (12) $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous.
- (13) $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) > 0$;
- (14) $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = 0 \iff \zeta = \xi$;
- (15) $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \varphi(\xi, \zeta, \varpi)$;
- (16) $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) \oplus \varphi(\xi, \tilde{v}, \mathbf{u}) \geq \varphi(\zeta, \tilde{v}, \varpi + \mathbf{u})$;
- (17) $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous.

A 6-tuple $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ is called $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$.

The functions $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi)$, $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi)$ and $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi)$ denote nearness degree, non-nearness degree and indeterminacy degree of ζ to ξ at ϖ , respectively.

Example 2.2. Let $\Omega = \mathfrak{I}R, \vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ and φ by $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ and for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{I}R, \kappa, \varrho, \odot, \oplus)$ is a $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$.

Definition 2.3. Let $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ be a $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$ and $\varpi > 0, \mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\zeta \in \Omega$. The set $\mathfrak{B}_\zeta(\mathfrak{v}, \varpi) = \{\xi \in \Omega : \kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}$ is described as an open sphere with center ζ and radius \mathfrak{v} with regard to ϖ .

Example 2.4. Let $\Omega = \mathfrak{I}R, \vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ and φ by $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ and for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{I}R, \kappa, \varrho, \odot, \oplus)$ is an $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$.

Now define a sequence (ζ_n) by $\zeta_n = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}, & n = \lambda^3, \lambda \in \mathfrak{I}N; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Then, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and for any $\varpi > 0$. we have (ζ_n) . Here $(\zeta_n) \in \mathfrak{B}_\zeta(0, \varpi)$.

Definition 2.5. Let $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ be a $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}$.

- (i) A sequence (ζ_n) is known to be convergent to ζ if for all $\varpi > 0$ and $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ there exists $n_0 \in \mathfrak{I}N$ so that $\kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}$ for every $n \geq n_0$. It is symbolised as $\zeta_n \rightarrow \zeta$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.
- (ii) $\odot\kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) \rightarrow 1, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) \rightarrow 0$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta, \varpi) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for each $\varpi > 0$.
- (iii) (ζ_n) is known to be a Cauchy sequence if, for $\varpi > 0$ and $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$, there is $n_0 \in \mathfrak{I}N$ such that $\kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}$ for all $n, m \geq n_0$.
- (iv) $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ is called $(\kappa, \varrho, \varphi)$ -complete if every Cauchy sequence is convergent.

Example 2.6. Let $\Omega = \mathfrak{I}R, \vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ and φ by $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ and for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{I}R, \kappa, \varrho, \odot, \oplus)$ is an $\mathfrak{I}\mathfrak{F}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$.

Now define a sequence (ζ_n) by $\zeta_n = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{n}}, & n = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathfrak{I}N; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Then, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and for any $\varpi > 0$,

$$\kappa(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}.$$

ζ_n is both convergent and Cauchy sequence in Ω .

Definition 2.7. Let (Ω, κ, \odot) be a $\mathfrak{F}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$.

- (1) A sequence $(\zeta_n) \subset \Omega$ is termed $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to $\zeta_0 \in \Omega$ if, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, the condition $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{J}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$ holds.
- (2) A sequence $(\zeta_n) \subset \Omega$ is referred to as $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}\mathfrak{a}$ if, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, there exists an $\mathfrak{m} \in \mathfrak{J}N$ such that $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{J}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 0$.

Example 2.8. Let $\Omega = \mathfrak{I}R, \vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ and φ by $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ and for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{I}R, \kappa, \varrho, \odot, \oplus)$ is an $\mathfrak{I}\mathfrak{F}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$.

Now define a sequence (ζ_n) by $\zeta_n = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{n}}{2}, & \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^3, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Then, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and for any $\varpi > 0$, let $\mathfrak{M} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \kappa(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \geq \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi} \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : |\zeta_n| \geq \frac{\mathfrak{v}\varpi}{1 - \mathfrak{v}} > 0\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \zeta_n = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{2}\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N\}$, and we obtain $\frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\mathfrak{M}| \leq \frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^3, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N\}| \leq \frac{\sqrt{\mathfrak{m}}}{\mathfrak{m}} \rightarrow 0, \mathfrak{m} \rightarrow \infty$. As a result, we have (ζ_n) is $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to 0 with regard to the $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$.

3. Static Convergence in Neutrosophic Metric Spaces

Definition 3.1. Let $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ be a $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$. A sequence $(\zeta_n) \subset \Omega$ is called $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to $\zeta_0 \in \Omega$ with respect to $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{M}$ obtained that, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{J}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$.

We assert that (ζ_n) is $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to ζ_0 . We can observe as $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{J}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$
 $\Leftrightarrow \lim_{\mathfrak{m} \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{\mathfrak{k} \leq \mathfrak{n} : \kappa(\zeta_{\mathfrak{k}}, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_{\mathfrak{k}}, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_{\mathfrak{k}}, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}|}{\mathfrak{n}} = 1$

Example 3.2. Let $\Omega = \mathfrak{I}R, \vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ and φ by $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}, \varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ and for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathfrak{I}R, \kappa, \varrho, \odot, \oplus)$ is an $\mathfrak{I}\mathfrak{F}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$.

Now define a sequence (ζ_n) by $\zeta_n = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Then, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and for any $\varpi > 0$, let $\mathfrak{M} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \kappa(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \geq \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi} \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : |\zeta_n| \geq \frac{\mathfrak{v}\varpi}{1 - \mathfrak{v}} > 0\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \zeta_n = 1\} = \{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N\}$, and we obtain $\frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\mathfrak{M}| \leq \frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\{\mathfrak{n} \leq \mathfrak{m} : \mathfrak{n} = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathfrak{J}N\}| \leq \frac{\sqrt{\mathfrak{m}}}{\mathfrak{m}} \rightarrow 0, \mathfrak{m} \rightarrow \infty$. As a result, we have (ζ_n) is $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to 0 with regard to the $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$.

Lemma 3.3. Let $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ be an $\mathfrak{N}\mathfrak{M}\mathfrak{S}$. Then, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$.

These are comparable to each other:

(i) (ζ_n) is $\mathfrak{S}\mathfrak{C}$ to ζ_0 ;

(ii) $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{J}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}\}) = \Delta(\{\varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}, \Delta(\{\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}\}) = 0\}) = 0$;

$$(iii) \Delta(\{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}\}) = \Delta(\{\varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}, \Delta(\{\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}) = 1.$$

Proof: Utilizing Definition (3.1) and we possess a lemma regarding density characteristics.

Theorem 3.4. *Let $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ be $\mathcal{NM}\mathcal{S}$. When a sequence (ζ_n) is $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}$ with regards to the \mathcal{NM} , then the $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}$ limit is unique.*

Proof: Let us consider (ζ_n) be $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}$ to ζ_1 and ζ_2 . Given $\mathbf{v} \in (0, 1)$, take $\varpi > 0$ such that $(1\varpi) \odot (1\varpi) > 1\mathbf{v}$ and $\varpi \oplus \varpi < \mathbf{v}$.

Then classify the following sets, for any $\epsilon > 0$:

$$\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_1, \epsilon) > 1 - \varpi\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 2}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \epsilon) > 1 - \varpi\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_1, \epsilon) < \varpi\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 2}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \epsilon) < \varpi\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_1, \epsilon) < \varpi\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 2}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{n \in \mathcal{I}N : \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \epsilon) < \varpi\}$$

Since (ζ_n) is $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}$ with respect to ζ_1 and ζ_2 , we get

$$\Delta\{\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 1}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 1}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 1}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = 1 \text{ and } \Delta\{\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = \Delta\{\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = 1, \text{ for every } \epsilon > 0.$$

$$\text{Let } K_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(\varpi, \epsilon) := \{\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\kappa 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} \cap \{\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varrho 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} \cap \{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varphi 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\}.$$

Therefore, $\Delta\{K_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = 1$ which implies that $\Delta\{\mathcal{I}N \setminus K_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} = 0$.

When $n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus K_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(\varpi, \epsilon)$, then there are two potential outcomes:

$$n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\kappa 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} \text{ or } n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varrho 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\} \text{ or } n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varphi 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\}.$$

Let us consider $n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\kappa 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\kappa 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\}$.

$$\text{Then we achieve } \kappa(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) \geq \kappa(\zeta_1, \zeta_n, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \odot \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) > (1 - \varpi) \odot (1 - \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}.$$

Therefore, $\kappa(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) > 1\mathbf{v}$ and since $\mathbf{v} > 0$ is arbitrary, we achieve $\kappa(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) = 1$ for all $\epsilon > 0$, which infers $\zeta_1 = \zeta_2$.

Let us consider $n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\varrho 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varrho 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\}$.

$$\text{Then, } \varrho(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) \leq \varrho(\zeta_1, \zeta_n, \epsilon) \oplus \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \epsilon) < \varpi \oplus \varpi < \mathbf{v}.$$

Since $\mathbf{v} > 0$ is arbitrary, we obtain $\varrho(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) = 0$ for all $\epsilon > 0$, which suggests $\zeta_1 = \zeta_2$.

Now let us consider $n \in \mathcal{I}N \setminus \{\mathcal{M}_{\varphi 1}(\varpi, \epsilon) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\varphi 2}(\varpi, \epsilon)\}$.

$$\text{Then, } \varphi(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) \leq \varphi(\zeta_1, \zeta_n, \epsilon) \oplus \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_2, \epsilon) < \varpi \oplus \varpi < \mathbf{v}.$$

Since $\mathbf{v} > 0$ is arbitrary, we obtain $\varphi(\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \epsilon) = 0$ for all $\epsilon > 0$, which refers $\zeta_1 = \zeta_2$.

Theorem 3.5. *Consider the sequence (ζ_n) in the Neutrosophic Metric Space $\mathcal{NM}\mathcal{S}$ $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. If (ζ_n) converges to ζ_0 with respect to the Neutrosophic Metric \mathcal{NM} , then (ζ_n) is $\mathcal{S}\mathcal{C}$ to ζ_0 in the context of the \mathcal{NM} .*

Proof: Let (ζ_n) be a sequence convergent to ζ_0 . Then, for every $\mathbf{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, there exists an $n_0 \in \mathcal{JN}$ such that $\kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}$, and $\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}$. We obtain $|\{\lambda \leq \mathbf{n} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v} \text{ and } \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}| \geq nn_0$.

Hence, the set $\{\lambda \leq \mathbf{n} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v} \text{ and } \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}$ has a finite number of terms.

Then, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{\lambda \leq \mathbf{n} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}|}{\mathbf{n}} \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{nn_0}{\mathbf{n}} = 1$.

Consequently, $\Delta(\{\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}) = 1$.

The converse of the theorem need not true.

Example 3.6. Let $\Omega = [1, 3]$, and define the operations $\vartheta \odot \omega = \vartheta\omega$ and $\vartheta \oplus \omega = \min\{\vartheta + \omega, 1\}$ for all $\vartheta, \omega \in [0, 1]$. Define κ, ϱ , and φ by the following formulas: $\kappa(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}$, $\varrho(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi + |\zeta - \xi|}$, and $\varphi(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \frac{|\zeta - \xi|}{\varpi}$ for all $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then $(\mathcal{JN}, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ forms a Neutrosophic Metric Space $(\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S})$.

Now define a sequence (ζ_n) by $\zeta_n = \begin{cases} 2, & \mathbf{n} = \lambda^2, \lambda \in \mathcal{JN}; \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$.

We can see that (ζ_n) is not convergent to 1.

We need to show that (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SC} to 1.

Let $\mathbf{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$. $\mathfrak{M} = \{\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}$.

Case 1. $\mathbf{v} \in (0, \frac{1}{\varpi+1}]$. If $n \neq \lambda^2$ for all $\lambda \in \mathcal{JN}$, then $\kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 1 > 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 0 < \mathbf{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 0 < \mathbf{v}$. If $\mathbf{n} = \lambda^2$ for some $\lambda \in \mathcal{JN}$, then $\kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi+1} = 1 - \frac{1}{\varpi+1} \leq 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{1}{\varpi+1} \geq \mathbf{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{1}{\varpi+1} \geq \mathbf{v}$.

Now, let $\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN}$. If $\mathbf{n} = \lambda_0^2$ for an $\lambda_0 \in \mathcal{JN}$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\mathfrak{M}(\mathbf{n})|}{\mathbf{n}} = \lim_{\lambda_0 \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_0^2 \lambda_0}{\lambda_0^2} = 1$. If $\mathbf{n} \neq \lambda^2$ for all $\lambda \in \mathcal{JN}$, Therefore, it follows that $\lambda_1 \in \mathcal{JN}$ such that $\mathbf{n} = \lambda_1^2 l$ with $l \in \mathcal{JN}$ and $1 \leq l \leq \lambda_1$. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\mathfrak{M}(\mathbf{n})|}{\mathbf{n}} = \lim_{\lambda_1 \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_1^2 l (\lambda_1 l)}{\lambda_1^2 l} = \lim_{\lambda_1 \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_1^2 \lambda_1 l + 1}{\lambda_1^2 l} = 1$.

Case 2. $\mathbf{v} \in (\frac{1}{\varpi+1}, 1)$. If $n \neq \lambda^2$ for all $\lambda \in \mathcal{JN}$, then $\kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 1 > 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 0 < \mathbf{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = 0 < \mathbf{v}$. If $\mathbf{n} = \lambda^2$ for some $\lambda \in \mathcal{JN}$, then $\kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{\varpi}{\varpi+1} = 1 - \frac{1}{\varpi+1} > 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{1}{\varpi+1} < \mathbf{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) = \frac{1}{\varpi+1} < \mathbf{v}$.

Hence, $\kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}$, $\varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}$ for all $\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN}$. Therefore,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\mathfrak{M}(\mathbf{n})|}{\mathbf{n}} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mathbf{n}}{\mathbf{n}} = 1.$$

Therefore, $\Delta(\{\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) > 1 - \mathbf{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 1, \varpi) < \mathbf{v}\}) = 1$ for all $\mathbf{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$.

Theorem 3.7. Consider the sequence (ζ_n) in the Neutrosophic Metric Space $\mathfrak{NM}\mathfrak{S}(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. The sequence (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SC} to ζ_0 if and only if there exists an increasing index sequence $\mathfrak{P} = \{\mathbf{n}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{JN}}$ of natural numbers such that $(\zeta_{\mathbf{n}_i})$ converges to ζ_0 and $\Delta(\mathfrak{P}) = 1$.

Proof: Given that the sequence (ζ_n) statistically converges to ζ_0 , define $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi) := \{\mathbf{n} \in \mathcal{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \frac{1}{j}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}, \text{ and } \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}\}$ for any $\varpi > 0$ and $j \in \mathcal{JN}$.

We establish that $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j + 1, \varpi) \subset \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi)$ for all $\varpi > 0$ and $j \in \mathfrak{JN}$. Since (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SC} to ζ_0 ,

$$\Delta(\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi)) = 1 \tag{1}$$

Take $u_1 \in \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(1, \varpi)$. Since $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(2, \varpi)) = 1$ (by Equation (1)) we have a number $u_2 \in (\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(2, \varpi)(u_2 > u_1)$ such that $\frac{|\{\lambda \leq n: \kappa(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \frac{1}{2}, \varrho(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{2}, \varphi(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{2}\}|}{n} > \frac{1}{2}$, for every $n \geq u_2$.

According to Equation (1), $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(3, \varpi)) = 1$. We can select $u_3 \in \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(3, \varpi)$ (where $u_3 > u_2$) such that for all $n \geq u_3$, the fraction $\frac{|\{\lambda \leq n: \kappa(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \frac{1}{3}, \varrho(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{3}, \varphi(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{3}\}|}{n} > \frac{2}{3}$.

We proceed in this manner.

Subsequently, we can construct an increasing sequence of indices $\{u_j\}_{j \in \mathfrak{JN}}$ from natural numbers such that each u_j belongs to $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi)$.

$$\frac{|\{\lambda \leq n : \kappa(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \frac{1}{j}, \varrho(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}, \varphi(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}\}|}{n} > \frac{j - 1}{j}, \tag{2}$$

for all $n \geq u_j$, where j ranges over \mathfrak{JN} . We define the increasing index sequence \mathfrak{P} as:

$$\mathfrak{P} := \{n \in \mathfrak{JN} : 1 < n < u_1\} \cup \left(\bigcup_{j \in \mathfrak{JN}} \{n \in \mathfrak{JN} : u_j \leq n < u_{j+1}\} \cap \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi) \right).$$

By Equation (2) and $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j + 1, \varpi) \subset \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(j, \varpi)$, we write

$$\frac{|\{\lambda \leq n : \lambda \in \mathfrak{P}\}|}{n} \geq \frac{|\{\lambda \leq n : \kappa(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \frac{1}{j}, \varrho(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}, \varphi(\zeta_\lambda, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \frac{1}{j}\}|}{n} > \frac{j - 1}{j}$$

for all $n, (u_j \leq n < u_{j+1})$.

Given that $j \rightarrow \infty$, at which $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\{\lambda \leq n: \lambda \in \mathfrak{P}\}|}{n} = 1$, i.e., $\Delta(\mathfrak{P}) = 1$.

Now, we demonstrate the convergence of (ζ_{n_i}) to ζ_0 . Let $v \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$. Choose $N_0 > u_2$ sufficiently large such that there exists an index $s_0 \in \mathfrak{JN}$ satisfying $u_{s_0} \leq N_0 < u_{s_0+1}$ and $\frac{1}{s_0} < v$. Consider $n_m \geq N_0$ where $n_m \in \mathfrak{P}$. By the definition of \mathfrak{P} , there exists $s \in \mathfrak{JN}$ such that $u_s \leq n_m < u_{s+1}$ and $n_m \in \mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(s, \varpi)$ (with $s \geq s_0$). Thus,

$$\kappa(\zeta_{n_m}, \zeta_0, \varpi) \geq \kappa\left(\zeta_{n_m}, \zeta_0, \frac{1}{s_0}\right) \geq \kappa\left(\zeta_{n_m}, \zeta_0, \frac{1}{s}\right) > 1 - \frac{1}{s} \geq 1 - \frac{1}{s_0} > 1 - v, \varrho(\zeta_{n_m}, \zeta_0, \varpi) > \frac{1}{s_0} < v$$

and $\varphi(\zeta_{n_m}, \zeta_0, \varpi) > \frac{1}{s_0} < v$. Therefore, (ζ_{n_i}) converges to ζ_0 .

On the otherhand, Let's suppose there exists a sequence of increasing indices $\mathfrak{P} = \{n_i\}_{i \in \mathfrak{JN}}$ of natural numbers such that $\Delta(\mathfrak{P}) = 1$ and (ζ_{n_i}) converges to ζ_0 . Take $v \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$. Then, there exists a number $n_0 \in \mathfrak{JN}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, the conditions $\kappa(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - v, \varrho(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) < v$, and $\varphi(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) < v$ are satisfied.

Let us define $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(v, \varpi) := \{n \in \mathfrak{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) \leq 1 - v \text{ or } \varrho(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) \geq v \text{ and } \varphi(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \varpi) \geq v\}$. We have $\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(v, \varpi) \subset \mathfrak{JN} \setminus \{n_0, n_{n_0+1}, n_{n_0+2}, \dots\}$. Since $\Delta(\mathfrak{P}) = 1$, we have $\Delta(\mathfrak{JN} \setminus \{n_0, n_{n_0+1}, n_{n_0+2}, \dots\}) = 0$, so we deduce $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}_{\kappa\varrho\varphi}(v, \varpi)) = 0$. Hence, $\Delta(\{n \in \mathfrak{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < 1 - v, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < v \text{ and } \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < v\}) = 1$.

Therefore, (ζ_n) \mathfrak{SC} to ζ_0 .

Corollary 3.8. *If (ζ_n) is a sequence within an $\mathfrak{NMS} (\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ that is both \mathfrak{SC} to ζ_0 and convergent, then (ζ_n) converges to ζ_0 .*

Definition 3.9. Let $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \varphi_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ and $(\Omega_2, \kappa_2, \varrho_2, \varphi_2, \odot_2, \oplus_2)$ be two \mathfrak{NMS} spaces.

- (i) A map $\chi : \Omega_1 \rightarrow \Omega_2$ is termed an isometry if for every $\zeta, \xi \in \Omega_1$ and $\varpi > 0$, $\kappa_1(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \kappa_2(\chi(\zeta), \chi(\xi), \varpi)$, $\varrho_1(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \varrho_2(\chi(\zeta), \chi(\xi), \varpi)$ and $\varphi_1(\zeta, \xi, \varpi) = \varphi_2(\chi(\zeta), \chi(\xi), \varpi)$.
- (ii) $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \varphi_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ and $(\Omega_2, \kappa_2, \varrho_2, \varphi_2, \odot_2, \oplus_2)$ are termed isometric if there exists a bijective mapping (an isometry) from Ω_1 to Ω_2 .
- (iii) A neutrosophic completion of $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ is defined as a complete $\mathfrak{NMS} (\Omega_2, \kappa_2, \varrho_2, \odot_2, \oplus_2)$ such that $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ is isometrically embedded as a dense subspace within Ω_2 .
- (iv) $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ is termed completable if it can be extended to form a complete \mathfrak{NMS} .

Proposition 3.10. *Suppose (ζ_n) is a sequence in a completable $\mathfrak{NMS} (\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. If (ζ_n) is a Cauchy sequence in Ω and it is statistically dense around ζ_0 , then (ζ_n) converges to ζ_0 .*

Proof: Let $(\Omega_1, \kappa_1, \varrho_1, \varphi_1, \odot_1, \oplus_1)$ be the completion of $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. Consequently, there exists $\zeta_1 \in \Omega_1$ such that the sequence (ζ_n) converges to ζ_1 . We have $\kappa_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) = \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi)$, $\varrho_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) = \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi)$ and $\varphi_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) = \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi)$ for all $\varpi > 0$ and $n \in \mathfrak{IN}$.

Let $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$. Since $\Delta(\{n \in \mathfrak{IN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v} \text{ and } \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$, we obtain $\Delta(\{n \in \mathfrak{IN} : \kappa_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v} \text{ and } \varphi_1(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$. Hence, we see that (ζ_n) statistically converges to $\zeta_0 \in \Omega_1$ with respect to $(\kappa_1, \varrho_1, \varphi_1)$. By Corollary (3.8), we have $\zeta_1 = \zeta_0$.

4. Statically Complete \mathfrak{NMS}

Definition 4.1. Consider a sequence $(\zeta_n) \subset \Omega$, where $(\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ is a \mathfrak{NMS} . The sequence is termed a \mathfrak{SCa} if, for every $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, there exists $\mathfrak{m} \in \mathfrak{IN}$ such that $\Delta(\{n \in \mathfrak{IN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_m, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$.

Example 4.2. In Example(2.4), $\mathfrak{M} = \{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : \kappa(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \varrho(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, 0, \varpi) \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : \frac{\varpi}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \leq 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi + |\zeta_n|} \geq \mathfrak{v}, \frac{|\zeta_n|}{\varpi} \geq \mathfrak{v}\} = \{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : |\zeta_n| \geq \frac{\mathfrak{v}\varpi}{1-\mathfrak{v}} > 0\} = \{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : \zeta_n = 1\} = \{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : n = \lambda^3, \lambda \in \mathfrak{IN}\}$, and we obtain $\frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\mathfrak{M}| \leq \frac{1}{\mathfrak{m}}|\{n \leq \mathfrak{m} : n = \lambda^3, n \in \mathfrak{IN}\}| \leq \frac{\sqrt[3]{\mathfrak{m}}}{\mathfrak{m}} \rightarrow 0, \mathfrak{m} \rightarrow \infty$. As a result, we have (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SC} to 0 with regard to the $\mathfrak{NMS} (\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$.

Theorem 4.3. *Let (ζ_n) denote a sequence within the framework of $\mathfrak{NMS} (\Omega, \kappa, \varrho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. The following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) (ζ_n) is classified as a \mathfrak{SCa} sequence.
- (ii) There exists a progressively increasing index sequence $\mathfrak{M} = \{n_i\}_{i \in \mathfrak{JN}}$ of natural numbers such that (ζ_{n_i}) is characterized by being Cauchy and achieving $\Delta(\mathfrak{M}) = 1$.

Proof: Direct

Theorem 4.4. Consider a sequence (ζ_n) within the framework of $\mathfrak{NMS}(\Omega, \kappa, \rho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$. If (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SC} with respect to the \mathfrak{NM} , then (ζ_n) is \mathfrak{SCa} with respect to the \mathfrak{NM} .

Proof: If (ζ_n) is statistically convergent to ζ_0 and for given $\mathfrak{v} \in (0, 1)$ and $\varpi > 0$, there exists $\mathfrak{v}_1 \in (0, 1)$ such that $(1 - \mathfrak{v}_1) \odot (1 - \mathfrak{v}_1) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}$ and $\mathfrak{v}_1 \oplus \mathfrak{v}_1 < \mathfrak{v}$. We have $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \rho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$. Refer Theorem (3.4), there exists an increasing index sequence $\{n_i\}_{i \in \mathfrak{JN}}$ so that (ζ_{n_i}) is convergent to ζ_0 . Hence, there exists $n_{i_0} \in \{n_i\}_{i \in \mathfrak{JN}} : \kappa(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}_1, \rho(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) < \mathfrak{v}_1$ and $\varphi(\zeta_{n_i}, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) < \mathfrak{v}_1$ for all $n_i \geq n_{i_0}$.

Since $\kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) \geq \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) \odot \kappa(\zeta_0, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \frac{\varpi}{2}) \geq (1 - \mathfrak{v}_1) \odot (1 - \mathfrak{v}_1) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}$, $\rho(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) \leq \rho(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) \oplus \rho(\zeta_0, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \frac{\varpi}{2}) < \mathfrak{v}_1 \oplus \mathfrak{v}_1 < \mathfrak{v}$ and $\varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) \leq \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_0, \frac{\varpi}{2}) \oplus \varphi(\zeta_0, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \frac{\varpi}{2}) < \mathfrak{v}_1 \oplus \mathfrak{v}_1 < \mathfrak{v}$, we have $\Delta(\{\mathfrak{n} \in \mathfrak{JN} : \kappa(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) > 1 - \mathfrak{v}, \rho(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}, \varphi(\zeta_n, \zeta_{n_{i_0}}, \varpi) < \mathfrak{v}\}) = 1$. Therefore, (ζ_n) is statistically Cauchy with respect to the \mathfrak{NM} .

Remark 4.5. Given that a sequence in a \mathfrak{NMS} is Cauchy, it consequently meets the criteria to be classified as \mathfrak{SCa} .

Definition 4.6. The $\mathfrak{NMS}(\Omega, \kappa, \rho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ is termed statistically complete if every \mathfrak{SCa} sequence in Ω is also \mathfrak{SC} .

Theorem 4.7. If $(\Omega, \kappa, \rho, \varphi, \odot, \oplus)$ is a \mathfrak{NMS} where Ω is statistically complete, then it is also complete according to the \mathfrak{NM} .

Proof: The proof follows a similar approach to Theorem (4.4).

5. Conclusion

This paper has discussed and proved some results of \mathfrak{SC} and \mathfrak{SCa} on \mathfrak{NMS} . Additionally looked at the attributes of statistical completeness on \mathfrak{NMS} . Our results can be extended to other spaces and be used to arrive at more results in fixed point theory.

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